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GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

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A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF OPEN SPACES AND THE LOCATION OF MECHANIC WORKSHOPS IN RESIDENTIAL OF AREAS OF AKURE TOWNSHIP

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Abstract: *This paper examines the roles of different groups or stakeholders in land use allocation to mechanic workshops in the residential areas of Akure Township. The paper adopted the method of descriptive and inference statistical methods in carrying out this research. The distributive statistical method employed 20% sampling size for selection of buildings where the respondents were selected from different housing units for questionnaire administration where frequency tables were used to elicit information on the role played by different group of people living in the residential areas on land allocation for mechanic workshops. Regression Analysis technique was used as an inference procedure that explained the relationship between a dependent or criterion variable of location of mechanic workshops and a set of independent or predictor variables opinion of urban residents. The information showed that the responsibilities of youth, adults, women, NGO/CBO, landlord and politicians groups that make a residential area in land allocation for mechanic workshops is inevitable. The paper recommended the active involvement of public/community in land allocation for different uses in study area is important. It also recommended the involvement of government agency such as planning authority at all level to coordinate the activities of these groups in order to a achieve a sustainable residential development Akure township.*

Key Words: Systematic, Review, Open Space, Location, Mechanic Workshop, Residential Areas

INTRODUCTION

The world population is growing at an annual rate of 1.3% (77 million per year) and more than 90% of the growth is taking place in cities of Developing Countries. It was estimated that 374.4 million are city dwellers in Africa in 2007 and is expected to hit 759.4 million by the year 2030 and possibly rising to 1.2 billion by 2050 (Habitat for Humanity, 2023). The unprecedented growth of cities in Africa has resulted into the growth of traditional local services and small scale business such as mechanic profession among other small scale industries of which the location of the workshops

are haphazardly distributed in the residential land use(Overseas Development Institute, 2008)

Mechanic business, it is among the services that attract large number of young people in the city. This is because the pattern of demand for the service can be easily met with increasing number of car owners thus, forming part of activities that dictate the pattern of urban physical development. Mechanic service is frequently carried out in traditional manner that is in poorly constructed workshops located on land uses such as open spaces, setback from road, streams or under electricity high tension in the residential area of cities. This was buttressed by World Bank (1989) reports that

25% of the open space set aside for community facilities such as electricity and communication lines, water pipe, recreation, sports, nature conservation among others are unsecured by government agencies but occupied by small scale business including mechanic workshops.

This is affirmed by the perception of the public that open spaces in residential areas are regarded as no man's land. Thus, widespread encroachment on open spaces and unauthorised places like government acquisition, setback, walkway and others by mechanic in urban centres of Nigeria become the site where mechanics workshops are located. Irrespective of this haphazard development, residents still patronise these services because of the advantage of proximity of providing services of doorstep and does not require them to follow rigorous protocol characterised by large organisation (Urwameiye and Iyamu, 2005).

Residential area is the largest consumer of land in urban land use. It covers between 50-60% comprising houses of various kinds ranging from detached houses, duplexes condominium, block of flats and bungalows to tenement houses of single rooms. Its density is determined by factors such as socio-economic (income), relief, technical, infrastructure, government policies and laws. The major element of residential land use is housing which comprises of all socially accepted ways by which a man acquires a territory for his home, the procedures by which he retain that territory and the manner in which the stock of houses is maintained and enlarged. Typically, certain amount of open space is required in any residential areas, based on longstanding assumptions about park use. This required amount of green or open space calculated according to formulas that formed the uniform planning standard in planning legislation and/or

policies. It therefore promotes planning standards and rules provided conventionally certainty in green space planning (Olurin, 2007).

Research has shown that many planning authorities failed to implement their planning standards on open spaces in Nigeria urban residential areas due to the pressure of traditional land use tenure. This is the reason why open spaces are allocated either temporarily or permanently allocated to mechanics for erection of their workshops. Moreover, in recent time, rising land values, estate tax pressures and increasing family responsibilities have resulted in the fragmentation, sale or lease of some parts of land properties for other developments such as location of mechanic workshops and other small scale business springing up in residential areas in Nigerian cities. This development has limited the benefit deriving from open space in the residential areas hence, degrading the environment (Lestan, Erzen and Golobic, 2014; Byrne and Sipe, 2016)

Growth of demand for the service of mechanic lead to the growth in demand for space for the erection of the workshops in residential area. In an attempt to explain the observed environmental consequent of growth in demand for space for these economic activities, there is need to understand the spatial location of these economic activities within the residential areas as it often said conceived all urban development initiatives are labelled environmental consequences. However, there is still much to learn from this local initiative in order to define its economic potential and urban land use consequences in the contest of location and distribution of mechanic workshops within residential areas (Satterthwaite, 2002 and Ubele, Martins and Tawee, 2013).

There is therefore the need for deep understanding of the potential of this profession and environmental problems arising from the location and pattern of distribution of mechanic workshops in open space areas and their effects on immediate environment in different residential areas of Akure Township. The focus of this paper to conduct research on locational pattern of the mechanic workshops the open space areas of residential areas of Akure bringing out the residents' perception on its effects and recommend a long-time solution for environmental problems resulting from it.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Residential areas in Nigeria cities have undergone profound reforms over recent decades, as politicians, decision makers, scholars and planners have sought to ensure that our built environments remain livable and can adapt to new lifestyles as population is growing. Urban consolidation is one of many reforms aimed at increasing population and maintaining sustainable economic development in existing built environments through smaller suburban residential schemes (public and private). Falade (1998) opined that the higher the rate of overcrowding in the Nigerian city as a result of high rate of urbanization the greater the deficiency of open spaces which consequently lead to ugly and unsaved environment and reduction in amenity.

Study shows city that city cannot function effectively without making adequate provision for buildings and open spaces for all the land use to retain most of its natural characteristic, recreation such as parks and publicly owned amenities and forest and agriculture lands. Furthermore, open spaces are public owned land that are set aside primarily for community

facilities such as electricity and communication lines, water pipe, recreation, sports, nature conservation, passive outdoor enjoyment and public gatherings. (Byrne and Sipe, 2016).

Open space (green space) is a key to happiness in the residential areas provides a range of social, environment and health benefits as well as making such areas more attractive. Thus, creation, protection and enhancement of joy and aesthetic are the main focus of open space and play a valuable role in sustainable urban development. The multiple benefits that green space provides can be categorised into ecological, social and economic benefits and overview of these benefits helps to contextualise green space acquisition and development. In order to be able to establish comfortable lifestyle for residents for low-income households in residential areas, use of open spaces for gardening activities, aqua-culture and recreation activities should be enhanced and incorporate small part of plot for small scale trade where mechanic workshops can be erected in the open spaces within the residential areas.

Therefore, it can be argued that the private appropriation of public space has two sides, firstly, it is illegal as it conflicts with existing laws and regulations because these open spaces belong to the government and on the other hand, it is an important strategy for a large number of city dwellers to sustain a living in the residential areas. Keeping this contradiction in mind, the term now refers to informal settlements visible in occupying the open spaces with illegal make-shift or temporary settlement for small scale business especially mechanic workshops (Wilhelm, 2012).

Mechanic workshop is located informally in residential areas of cities in Nigeria without conforming to zoning or service regulation but enabled by corrupt practices of planning

authorities, land owners or land speculators who hope for eventual regularisation and compensation for their investment. However keeping the benefits of open space to the residential areas in mind, urban dwellers still patronise prefer to patronise the services rendered in the mechanic workshop because of the advantage of providing services of repairing the car or lorries that does not require rigorous protocol characterised by large organisation, proximity to the car owners in the residential areas and provide job for mechanics training ground especially youths willing to learn the profession (Marxist Geography, 2004, Urwameiye and Iyamu, 2005).

The mechanic workshop is made up of wide space and a small shop built with temporary

METHODOLOGY

Data for this study was obtained from two main sources; primary and secondary. The primary data were obtained through structured questionnaire administration on the residents. Other primary instruments were as personal observation and direct interview on various groups of people Akure township as well in land use management for allocation of spaces for the mechanic workshops in residential areas of Akure Township. In view of this classification, the township was divided into 27 residential areas using express and arterial roads as boundaries that comprise both traditional; transition and periphery Systematic sampling technique was used to select 7 out of 27 residential areas and buildings represent 25.9% rounded up to be 26% random where respondents are selected for the interview and questionnaire administration which means the residential areas and indeed the buildings in Akure Township constitute the sampling frame.

buildings materials ranging from wood, iron sheets, mud and mud brick where tools like spanners, rings and others are kept thus the buildings generally violated three central elements of building codes; minimum required standards for construction materials, lots size and floor area (Lim, 2007). The workshop accommodates related professional such as automobile mechanic, rewire, panel beater, air conditioner, glass repair, and spray painter, body builder and vulcanizer that generate noise, land, water and air pollution. Nevertheless, common practice by the government in Nigerian cities and towns is to allocate large portions of land little bit far from residential to groups of small scale auto-mechanic businesses and designated this as mechanic village with repair yards offer their services (Nwachukwu et.al, 2013).

Systematic sampling was used due to the numbering of population numerically according to some convenient system and in this case 4th term was used to select areas for this study in this case one out of every four areas was chosen for this research (See figure 1 and Table 1). The selected areas now cut across the three zones (core, transitional and the periphery). According to Oyinloye et. al. (2017), the three zones were developed in the following years from the generation or settler to 1972 (zone 1), oil boom to second republic 1986 (zone 2) and dispensation of democracy 2020 and above (zone 3) The selected areas were distributed as follows:

Zone1 is indigenous core or traditional Core number (1-4)

Zone 2 is transitional (5-13)

Zone 3 is periphery (14-27)

The number of mechanics is shown in table 1

Table 1: Selected Residential Land use of Akure Town and the number of Mechanical Workshops occupied spaces in them.

S/N	Area	No of Mechanic Workshop	No of Selected Areas
1.	Town hall	8	
2.	Youth centre	4	
3.	Arakale	10	
4.	Oba's place	6	6
5.	Ijapo	7	
6.	Okuta Elerinnla	3	
7.	NPF headquarter	3	
8.	Akure Comm. College	8	8
9.	St. Michael Sec. Sch.	4	
10.	NPFB-Division	4	
11.	Aquinas college	4	4
12.	Bank Area	4	
13.	College of Agric.	5	
14.	Oba-Ile	5	
15.	Shasha Market	4	
16.	Shagari village	5	5
17.	NNPC Area	4	
18.	Road Block	5	
19.	FUTA Area	6	
20.	Ondo Garage	18	18
21.	Military Acquisition	4	
22.	Adefure Area	6	
23.	Alakure high School	5	
24.	Ijoka Area	10	
25.	School of Nursing	3	3
26.	Igbatoro	6	
27.	Alagbaka	4	
Total		153	51

Sources: Field Survey 2022

Source: Author' Graphic 2022
Figure 1: Selected residential areas of Akure for this research

It was assumed that 20% sample of buildings from each of selected areas would be representative hence, one out of 20 buildings were chosen for the interview and questionnaire administration where at least one respondent from a building was selected for the interview and questionnaire administration. Such information obtained are classified as follows: socio-economic characteristics of the urban dwellers, level of involvement in land use management and environmental perception of mechanic operations.

This research employed descriptive and inferential statistics to analyse the data collected. Descriptive statistics used in this study including frequency distribution and tables. While inference statistics were the procedures for testing hypothesis and was employed to arrive at broader generalization or inference. The reason for adopting this method is that data from the population from which samples were drawn is normally distributed and data were collected on normal, ordinal, interval and ratio. In this case regression analysis technique as a parametric statistics was used as an analytical procedure that explained the relationship between a dependent or criterion variable (location of mechanic workshops) and a set of independent or predictor variables (opinions of group of people).

The secondary data sources are the information that were obtained from library, internet, National population (NPC), National Bureau of Statistics, Ministry of Land and Housing on map of Akure and planning regulations and practice in all three tiers of government.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Table 2 shows that 30% of the respondents are between the ages 31-45 years followed by 40%

within the range 46-60-year-old and only 0% are in the ages of 16-30 years old. From this trend, it is clear that the working population who can afford to rent and acquire land for building houses dominating the household head in the residential areas of Akure Township. With respect to marital status, 80.4% respondents are married followed by 5.9% single, separated and widows. This indicates the respondents are of marriageable class and therefore have higher family responsibilities to carry leaving little or no amount for saving. It also reveals that vocational/apprenticeship such as mechanic forms the majority (70.6 %) of urban residents. Others are 11.8% secondary school certificate holders and 7.8% that are in the category of primary school leaving certificate respectively.

These categories of people are those who could not be employed as messengers or clerk who feel the salary paid to the low cadre is too low in civil service and large establishment or from the population that are to daily paid/profit job. Majority of the respondents interviewed (66.7%) earned between ₦18,000 - ₦36,000 per month followed by 21.6% who earned below ₦13,000 below the minimum wage when this research was conducted while the rest (6%) earned ₦36,001- ₦54,000 monthly. Therefore residents of selected areas for interview could be classed as low and medium incomes group in the society and such population cannot afford to sustain high standard of living therefore using land rent to complement his income is inevitable.

Also, research shows that the status of the respondents in selected residential area 30% of the respondents are free from all forms of falling health and another 30% claimed they have frequent high blood pressure (HBP) found among 46 years and above. Follow this is 15% that have pneumonia resulting from cold and 10% are suffering from arthritis while obesity

and diabetics carrying 5% each. This implies that those who need recreational facilities as supplementary therapy to orthodox or traditional medical care are many in the residential areas and open places for such project within their vicinity cannot be substituted for mechanic workshops and other non-residential activities.

But in recent time properties such as open space found to have higher value, estate tax pressure and increasing family responsibilities have resulted to fragmentation sale or lease this land for mechanic workshop other than recreational uses. The 55% of respondents who are politicians indicates that urban residents in Nigeria is waking up from the ideological reference of relevance of politics in environmental spending land use for project benefiting the community instead of using the space for mechanic workshops while liberal or non-politicians are more likely feeling warmly towards on open space as non-depreciable and non-reproductive asset. Basorun (2015) opined that making of an acceptable or popular land use plan require adequate study of both the manifestoes of political parties, their ideology and identification of key politicians in the residential area representing the people in the federal, state and local government in location and provision of resources in an area.

The NGO/CBO sees open spaces as public goods and common property that need to be

preserved because of resources of goods of clean water, clean air, biological diversity and scenic. The research give vivid account of NGO/CBO present in residential area of Akure Township and their opinion on the uses of open spaces in residential areas. From the table, 40% of the NGO/CBO is religion group, comprises Christian, Muslim and Traditional. The Christian used open space for aesthetic value; Muslim uses it as prayer places during festivals while the traditional use it for observing traditional festival or worshipping idol. Following this are 40%, 30% and 25% who are Landlord, Religion and Professional respectively. The interview shows that religion group are unable to compromise in releasing land for location of mechanic workshop due to noise and air pollution generated due the operation of their work while spaces owned by landlord or professional groups found easy to be reuse for mechanic workshop so as to use the rent as the value is rising.

Most of the respondents interviewed in the selected areas own at least one or more car/ lorry. The research shows that 70% of the respondents have 1-2 cars while 30% have no car or lorry at all. This affected the opinions of the residents as many car or lorry owners are in support of using open spaces for mechanic workshop for easy accessibility to car services and repair and supplementing rent for fuelling during removal of fuel subsidies by the government.

Table 2; Socio-Economic Characteristic of the Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age			Educational Attainment	Frequency	%
Below 15	0	0	No formal educational	1	5
15 – 30	0	0	Primary	3	15
31 – 45	6	30	Vocational	4	20
46 – 60	8	40	Secondary	4	20
61 and above	6	30	Technical	3	15
Total	20	100	OND	1	5
			HND/B.Sc	4	20
			Total	20	100

Marital Status of Mechanics

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Marital status	Frequency	%	Monthly Income (₦)	Frequency	%
Single	4	7.8	Below 15000	4	20
Married	41	80.4	18,000-36000	7	35
Separated	3	5.9	36000-54000	7	35
Widow/widower	3	5.9	54000-72000	2	10
Total	51	100	72000-90000	0	0
			90000-108000	0	0
			Above 108000	0	0
			Total	20	100

Political Level

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Political Liberality	8	40	NGO/CBO	Frequency	%
Politician	11	55	Not at all	1	5
Others	1	5	Landlord Association	8	40
Total	20	100	Youth Movement	0	
			Religion Group	6	30
			Environmental Group	5	25
			Total	20	100
			Cars / lorries owner	Frequency	%
			No car/lorry	14	70
			1 – 2	6	30
			3-4	0	0
			Total	20	100

Source: Author's Field work 2022

Investigating the opinions of the following set of people with respect to age, sex, educational attainment, income, health status, political liberal, NGO/CBO and car/lorry ownerships on and preference to use open space in residential areas for mechanic workshop in Akure Township using multiple regression models. Multiple Regression analysis was used to predict the significant relationship between the variables of opinion or the preference to use open space for location of mechanic workshops. The independent variables of socio-economic variables selected for model are the opinion of the group of people that has relationship with the dependent variable preference to use open space for the location of mechanic workshop. The variables are age, sex, education, income, health, political level and NGO/CBO and car/lorry owner. The general model for the analysis is as follows;

$$y = A + b_1x_i + b_2x_{ii} + b_3x_{iii} + b_4x_{iv} + b_5x_v + b_6x_{vi} + b_7x_{vii} + b_8x_{viii} \dots \dots \dots b_kx_k \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. (i)}$$

Where y = dependent variables say location of mechanic workshop

A is a constant or Y intercept and

$x_i, x_{ii}, x_{iii}, x_{iv}, x_v, x_{vi}, x_{vii}$ and x_{viii} are variables age, sex, education, income, health status,

political liberality, NGO/CBO and car/lorry owner respectively

b_1, b_2, b_3 are unit of changes in the independent variables of the respondent (opinion of group of people). $b_k x_k$ are b coefficients and y is the location of mechanic workshop (dependent) variable respectively. R^2 is the multiple regression coefficients that are used for variation that exist in the opinion of the people on mechanic workshops being located in the open spaces of residential areas.

$$y = (-.057)(age) + (-.766)(sex) + (-.062)(educational\ level) + (-.340)(income) + (-.007)(health\ status) + (-.006)(political\ liberality) + (.079)(NGO/CBO) + (.465)(car/lorry\ owner).$$

This means that an increase in y is experienced in this case. That is to say any increase in y (location of mechanic workshop) results from willingness to increase in supporting the uses of open space for mechanic workshop in the residential areas.

Table 3: Regression Analysis of opinions of stakeholders or group of peoples and decision to allocate land for Mechanic Workshops in the Residential Areas of Akure Township.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. error	Beta		
Age	-.571	.0000	-.086	.000	.000
Sex	-.766	.0000	-.660	.000	.000
Educational level	.062	.000	.210	.000	.000
Income	-.340	.000	-.642	.000	.000
Health	-.007	.000	-.028	.000	.000
Political	-.006	.000	-.006	.000	.000
NGO/CBO	.079	.000	.227	.000	.000
Car/lorry owner	.465	.000	.346	.000	.000

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2022

The summary of the model presented in Table 4 indicates that the significant opinions of the residents' variables represented by age, sex, education, income, health status, political liberality, NGO/CBO and car/lorry owner groups were able to predict the variation in 'location of mechanic workshop' It is a strong prediction for R^2 as 0.9210 (92.1%) and the

adjusted R^2 value as 0.9597. This shows that independent variable opinions of stakeholders in the residential areas in the model accounted for 92.1% variance in the independent variables is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that the moderate model fit at 7.9% left for other unexplained factors in the study area.

Table 4; Model Summary of Opinion of the residence and the location of mechanic workshop.

R	R^2	Adjusted R^2	std. error
0.9597	0.9210	.000	.000

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2022

Dependent variable: location mechanic workshop.

Predictor: constant, opinion of the residents

VARIABLES OF PUBLIC OPINION OF STAKEHOLDERS INFLUENCING THE LOCATION OF MECHANIC WORKSHOPS IN RESIDENTIAL AREAS OF AKURE TOWNSHIP

The eight-variable influencing the uses of open spaces for mechanic workshops in residential areas of Akure Township are age, sex, education, income level, health status, NGO/CBO, political liberality as well as car owners in residential areas of Akure Township with the reason is that different group of people living in the built environments will have different opinion on the space needs. In Table 3, there is negative relationship between the age group of people and the location of mechanic workshop in the selected residential areas. The result shows that the model was able to predict variation in people opinion on the preference to locate mechanic workshops in residential areas with significant socio-economic. It is moderately strong predictor for $R^2 = -.571$ (57.1%) is statistically significant at $p > 0.0000$.

This shows that the opinion of independent variable age in the model accounted for 57% variance in the dependent variable people opinion. This means that as the age is increasing the older people are less inclined to the uses of open spaces for recreation, health and fear of other users instead temporarily lease it to mechanics to build workshop and the money realized is used to supplement his income. Also, due to lack of financial support from family, government, CBO/NGO or financial institution to establish business and acquire site for workshop, youths especially mechanics take a decision of locating his workshop in any open space within the residential area hence develop informal settlement.

Sex variation is another factor that influences the location of mechanic workshop in the study

area. This factor displays a negative coefficient of $R^2 = -.766$ (76.6%) and this is statistically significant at 0.0000. This implies that home keeping, child caring and business activities help women and these activities does not allow them to show any interest on open space management and uses instead, it is used for building shopping complex for home base business and restaurants. Additional, Yoruba culture does not give free hand for women to decide on the matter related to land use management hence contributed little or nothing to land use management. However, activities of building restaurants and shopping complex and mechanic workshops are allocated together in the residential areas therefore the opinion of women support allocation of land for mechanic workshop.

Another factor that influences the people opinion in the residential areas is educational attainment. Also in table 3, there is positive relationship between the opinions based on educational attainment. This factor displays a coefficient estimate of 0.062 which indicate that it is statistically insignificant at $p > 0.0000$ and 6.2 % which indicate that irrespective of level of education, location of mechanic workshop in the residential area does not bother this group of people as long as they have easy access to service their car.

Moreover, income level is another environmental based opinion of location of mechanic workshop in the residential areas of Akure Township. Also, there is negative relationship between the opinion of income of the residents and preference of allocation of land for mechanic workshop. This factor shows a coefficient estimate of -.340 which means that a 100% increase in income level of the residents will reduce location of mechanic workshop in the residential area by 34% ($R^2 = 34\%$). This implies that with high income there is tendency that buildings of high income

earnings close to mechanic workshop may be renovated in other enhance its value thereby force eviction may be issued to mechanic working very close the building in order to enhance the property value. Also as income is increasing, abandoned housing project and new one may be raised in the residential areas thus vacant plots of land used for mechanic workshops are substituted with new building that was originally planned for.

Additionally, there is weak negative (-.2730) relationship between the health status of the resident and the location of mechanic workshops in the residential area. This health status increases by 100% will lead to a corresponding decrease of 27.3% ($R^2 = -.2730$). This indicates that people with better access to parks and other open space have been shown to live longer less stresses to illness and overweight. Open spaces that are less used for parks and recreation facilities but for location of mechanic workshops. This shows that site for recreational exercise and planting of fruits especially in the outskirts of residential areas are lacking because they have been used for mechanic workshops and others led to prominent of sickness like hypertension and regular high blood pressure in the residential areas.

Concomitantly, political liberality plays important role in location of social and economic activities on land in built environment of residential areas. Reference to Table 3, there is a weak negative (-.3620) relationship between the opinion of the politician and location of mechanic workshops in the residential areas of Akure Township. The coefficient of determination $R^2 = -.3620$ determines the proportion of the dependent variable location of mechanic workshops that is due to political liberality's opinion. When $R^2 = 36.2\%$ (i.e., $-.3620$ multiply by 100) representing the percentage of the dependent variable that is

due to the effect of political liberality and non-representative of elected member in the power led to low level of government intervention in land allocation for mechanic workshop. This result indicates that low level of political power apathy in the residential areas led to lack of government intervention on land use matter in study area which result to abuse of open space by location of mechanic workshop.

The influence of NGO/CBO on the location of mechanic workshops in the study area in Akure Township cannot be overlooked. There is positive relationship (.279) between the opinions of NGO/CBO in the residential area and location of mechanic workshops as indicated in Table 3. This result implies that there is correspondence increase of 27.9 % in the number of mechanic workshops in the areas. This is expected because the opinions of religious people, landlords, trade union and professional the car owners in the residential areas and members of the trade union dominate the decision making in the location of mechanic workshops in the study area. The uses of land for religion such as Muslim praying ground, building of churches and evil (*igbo igbale*) forest reserve within urban area for traditional religion are not given room for mechanic workshop to expand in the residential area of Akure Township.

Another factor influencing the location of mechanic workshops in the residential areas in Akure is the opinion of car owners. From the coefficient of determination is $R^2 = .465$ which determine the proportion of dependent variable of people opinion that is due to the effect of independent variable opinion of car and lorry owner in the residential area. When $R^2 = 46.5\%$ (i.e. $.465$ times 100) representing the percentage of dependent variable that is due to the effect of independent variable of 46.5% of location of

mechanic workshops in the study area. This indicates that there is increase in the number of car/lorry owners as a result of increase in salary, wages and profit earning in the business enterprises resulted in rising in purchasing power of the citizens to acquire more cars and lorries and hence increasing the number of mechanic workshop in the study area as long as it is proximity to them.

PERCEPTION OF ENVIRONMENT ON LOCATION OF MECHANIC WORKSHOPS IN RESIDENTIAL AREAS OF AKURE

Pollution ranges from air, water, land and noise are related to mechanic workshop thereby resulting in environmental degradation in residential area of Akure township. Properties such as building and land located near mechanic workshop in Akure township in are always loose value quickly in area where mechanic workshops are located close to a building. There is always agglomeration of economic as many related businesses such as motor spare part dealers, engine, break and gear oil were attracted by mechanic workshop hence increase population in residential areas is thereby bringing rising in house rent, prices of goods and services and worse is traffic congestion.

Where there is agglomeration of economic of scale as a result of mechanic workshops, there is always pressure on limited number of housing facilities such as toilet, water and electricity resulting in defecation in the drainage and the nearby bush digging of shallow well and epileptic electricity supply.

To crown it all on agglomeration of economic of scale, there is development of temporary buildings along the road and other open spaces resulting in shanty town or informal settlement and this obvious in Ilesa garage and Car Street in Akure Township.

Since the decision of land use management in most of the residential is made by these stakeholders with little or no government intervention resulted in informal settlement development as many buildings are built with temporary materials leading to slum development. Generally, these building materials violated three central elements of building codes; minimum required, standards for construction materials, minimum lot size and floor area and not conformity to planning standard (Lim, 2007). A site once used for mechanic workshop loose fertility fast and unable to grow flower or landscape for community garden and decoration of outside environment due to accumulation of engine oil hence, not suitable for landscaping. This is obvious in the settlements located along express roads of Ilesa – Owo and Ondo- Ore. Conflict always arose between the mechanic and land owner when he refuses to leave or pay rent on the rented or lease site for workshop.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Public participation of groups such as youths, aged, sex, Non-Governmental Organisation and Community Based Organisation (NGO/CBO) and occupational on land use policies and preparation of master plan in the residential areas of Akure Township is inevitable. Town planning Authority at the various level should review the existing Akure master plan and adopt comprehensive master plan to assign number of sites for mechanic workshops in residential area. Any excess mechanic workshop should be regarded as encroachment on land the development control department (DCD) in the Planning Authority should be served with contravention notice as a force eviction The DCD of Town Planning Authority should additionally carry out these functions to control the excesses of mechanics in the residential areas of Akure Township;

The DCD should adhere to the implementation of approved and operative physical development plan in the residential areas of Akure Township in order to avoid illegal structures resulting from agglomeration of economic of scale of mechanic workshops. The DCD should urgently within a stipulated time attend to various petitions and complaints on issues related to illegal development like mechanic workshop encroaching the residential land use and development on urban planning from the residents. The DC also should involve the law enforcement agents to carry out his eviction order to forcefully reduce mechanic workshop that their location is not compliancy with planning order.

Utilities such as public toilet, electricity street light and security should be provided where there is agglomeration of economic of scale resulted from location of mechanic workshops in residential areas so as to check the indiscriminating defecation in the nearby bush and gutters in the night by mechanics, joining men and apprentices, illumination along the street to check excesses of thieves and arm rubbers in the night to reduce stealing of spare parts and breaking of spare part shops.

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